
A Critical Analysis on the Procedure of Dispute Resolution Mechanism of World Trade Organization (WTO)

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ABSTRACT

Currently, at intergovernmental level WTO has become one of the most essential and efficient global trade organisations. Its role is not limited as a forum for continuous trade negotiations showcasing the importance of global economy, but it also acts as a watchdog that oversees and administers a complex matrix of international treaty law. In today's world it is operating as the most effective dispute resolution and settlement system at global level. In spite of the importance and prominence in trade dispute settlements, WTO is poorly understood by many. Hence there arises a need for an explanation on the basis of the WTO and how it functions as an organisation, and the scope of its authority and powers. It also requires to explain the role of the dispute settlement mechanism under the WTO. The dispute settlement system of the WTO functions relatively efficient, and in any event much speedier than many domestic judicial systems. It is said that the new trade rules of the WTO generally favour the developed countries. It is reported that the WTO Panel Reports and Appellate Body decisions exceed their authority and are legislated through their interpretation of WTO Rules. WTO Dispute Settlement Mechanism is considered to be one of the most essential developments of international economic

relations of the 20th century. It is also the strength of the WTO. The paper will provide a basic understanding on how evolution of dispute settlement mechanism took place and also discuss the roles, principles, machinery and proceedings related to dispute settlement body; while analysing its role in ensuring global justice.

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PART I: INTRODUCTION

International trade is highly complex, and is more complex than domestic trade. International trade involves more than one national law, rules and policies. There are over 200 countries in the world trading with other countries in a large number of goods and services. WTO is an international body dealing with the rules and regulations of trade among nations. The main object of WTO. is to liberalise trade among nations. “Our objectives is to anchor these countries in the ideal of freedom; economic as well as political. And so we are striving for free trade not just because it is good for America, but because it is good for all mankind¹.

Understanding on Rules and Procedures Governing the Settlement of Dispute. It offers a means for the settlement of dispute among Members of the WTO, that is unique in international agreements. ²The debate over the role of the law and adjudication in international affairs has a special dimension in the field of economic relations. International economic law, unlike classical international law, finds its foundation not on the concept of state’s sovereignty but on the notion of economic interdependence. ³It is also said that all politics is local and all economics is international.

The agreements of World Trade Organisation (WTO) established an autonomous body for settlement of disputes among Member countries of the WTO in trade matters at the governmental level. This body or institution is known by the name Dispute Settlement Body (DSB). This system of dispute settlement of WTO is considered as the best international agreement on matters of trade disputes at the international level. Settlement of dispute on time and structured basis is important. This system helps to prevent the detrimental effects of unresolved international trade conflicts, and mitigate the imbalances between the

¹ Devender Sharma, GATT and India; The politics of Agricultural by Devinder Sharma, p.3.

² WTO Singapore ministerial declaration adopted on 13, December 1996; WT/MIN/96/December.

economically rich and poor Members of the WTO, by having their disputes settled on the basis of rules rather than power determine the outcome.

After its commencement the dispute settlement system soon gained practical importance as its members increasingly resorted to using the dispute settlement system for settlement of their trade disputes. It provides a forum for continued trade negotiations and a super legal authority of the global trading system. The WTO oversees and administers a complex matrix of international treaty law. It operates and carries out the most complex and perhaps the most important international dispute settlement mechanism the world over.

PART II: DEVELOPMENT OF DISPUTE SETTLEMENT MECHANISM IN WTO.

In this part, the researcher would like to throw light on the evolution of the WTO Dispute Settlement System. The Dispute settlement mechanism of the WTO is considered to be one of the best international agreements ever made. The best international agreement is one, in which its parties to the agreements are willing to comply with such obligations due to the result of adjudication or otherwise, during the course of settlement of dispute by a competent authority. On the other hand, if one of the signatories of an international agreement fails to comply with such obligation, that agreement is not valid. An effective mechanism to settle disputes increases the practical value of the commitment undertaken by the signatories to the international agreement. The present dispute settlement system, established by the Members of the WTO during the Uruguay Round of Multilateral Trade negotiations, underscores the high importance they attach to compliance by all Members with their obligations under the WTO Agreement.

WTO has brought out two innovations⁴ i.e.,

- (i) 'Operational innovations'
- (ii) 'Institutional innovations'

Past experience has proved that the consensus rule granted a veto power to each and every Contracting Party, who wanted to defeat the panel process and the surveillance process, if it was against the party's will. This rule resulted in weakening the whole GATT norms and doctrines. If the WTO has to work effectively, the first reform of consensus rule has to be removed, and to save WTO from being

⁴ Komuro, Norio, The WTO Dispute Settlement Mechanism Coverage and Procedures of the WTO understanding, 29, Journal of World Trade 4th, August (1995) and reprinted in Journal of International Arbitration at 115 (1996).

crumbled, the DSU adopted negative Consensus rule. According to this negative consensus rule, 'suo moto' the panels are formed, the decisions of panel and appellate body are adopted, and the surveillance process is effectuated, unless decided by consensus not to do that.

Under GATT 1947, there was no formal dispute settlement institution. The GATT Article XXII and XXIII were not adequate to provide detailed rules and procedures for settlement of dispute as the GATT council characterized a diplomatic body rather than a judicial body. Unlike the GATT 1947 Understanding and Decisions, WTO Agreement established an autonomous body or institution for settlement of dispute. i.e., Dispute Settlement Body (DSB) and Dispute Settlement Understanding (DSU).⁵ As a noticeable achievement of Uruguay Round, the dispute settlement mechanism became considerably judicial in nature.⁶

The nucleus and vital part of the WTO institutional structure is the dispute settlement procedure derived from decades of experiments and practice in the GATT, but now, the new treaty text of the DSU, is a part of the WTO charter. Over the last fifteen years, many countries have come to recognise the crucial role that dispute settlement plays for any treaty system. Dispute settlement procedures assist in making rules effective, adding an essential measure of predictability and effectiveness to the operation of a rule-oriented system in the otherwise relatively weak realm of international norms.

The GATT Contracting Parties resolved at the 1986 launching meeting of the Uruguay Round to deal with some of the defects and problems existing in the dispute settlement rules. The result of that resolve was the new DSU.⁷ The aim of the dispute settlement mechanism is to secure a positive solution to a dispute. A solution mutually acceptable to the parties to dispute and consistent with the covered agreements is clearly to be preferred. In the absence of a mutually agreed solution, to secure the withdrawal of the measures concerned, the provisions of any of the covered agreements are found to be inconsistent. The provision of compensation should be resorted to only if the immediate withdrawal of the measure is impracticable.

⁵ Getlan, Myles, TRIPS and the Future of Section 301. A Comparative Study in Trade Dispute Resolution, 34 column. J. Transnt'l L.1.203.

⁶ 6 Schede, Christian. The Strengthening of the Multilateral System, 20 World Competition 1, at 111 (1996).

⁷ Croley Steven P & Jackson, John H; WTO Dispute Procedures, Standard of Review, and Deference to National Governments, 90 AJIL. 2 at 193.

The last resort which this understanding provides to the Member invoking the dispute settlement procedures, is the possibility of suspending the application of concessions or other obligations under the covered agreements on a discriminatory basis vis-à-vis the other Member subject to authorization by the DSB of such measures⁸. So both pragmatic and judicial solutions of dispute are obvious under this mechanism. One of the most contentious issues during the Uruguay Round was the DSU and its effect upon sovereignty of nations.⁹It was because the new dispute settlement mechanism vitiated the veto system and demanded obligation from Members to legislate in conformity with the WTO.

¹⁰The US Congress mandated the US negotiators in the Uruguay Round. The main aim of US in the Uruguay Round was to establish a binding and automatic dispute resolution system replacing the old GATT.¹⁸² While the US House of representatives on 29 November 1994, and the Senate on 1 December 1994 voted for Uruguay Round implementation of legislation, the debate centred on the issue of DSU and its impact on the US sovereignty.¹⁸³ These facts also prove the potential role and innovative character of DSU in multilateral trading system. The institutional frame work of the DSU also meaningfully resembles to the stratified local judicial structure. At the top is the Dispute Settlement Body, and below that, is the Appellate Body and below the Appellate Body there is a Panel.

PART III: FUNCTIONS OF WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT

The WTO agreements provide for many far-reaching rules concerning international trade in goods, trade in services and trade-related aspects of intellectual property rights. The WTO dispute settlement institutions function very much like a court of international trade. It has compulsory jurisdiction. It has its own rules of law. Its decisions are binding on the parties and sanction may be imposed against non-observance of its decision. The WTO has a remarkable system to settle the disputes between WTO Members concerning their rights and obligations under the WTO Agreement.

Some of the disputes brought before the WTO dispute settlement system have triggered considerable controversy and public debate, and have attracted much media attention.

⁸ Article 3.7 of the DSU.

⁹ Horlick, Gray N. WTO Dispute settlement and the Dole Commission, 29, J. World Trade 6 at 45 (1995).

¹⁰ Article XVI.4 of the WTO Agreement.

This has been the case, for example, for dispute on national legislation for the protection of public health or the environment, such as¹¹

3.1: CASES

- ‘The EC-Hormones dispute on the European communities, import ban on meat for cattle treated with growth hormones.’
- ‘The US-shrimp dispute on the US import ban on shrimp harvested with nets that kill sea turtles¹².’
- ‘The EC-Asbestos dispute on a French ban on asbestos and asbestos containing products¹³
- ‘The EC approval and Marketing of Biotech Products, dispute on measures affecting the approval and marketing of genetically modified products in the European Union¹⁴.’

3.2: ‘OBJECTS AND PURPOSE OF THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT SYSTEM’

The principal object and purpose of the WTO dispute settlement system is the prompt settlement of disputes between WTO Members, with respect to their rights and obligations under the WTO law.

‘Article 3.3 of the DSU states that the prompt settlement of such disputes “is essential to the effective functioning of the WTO and the maintenance of proper balance between the rights and obligations of Members.”’

‘Article 3.2 of the DSU states: “The dispute settlement system of the WTO is a central element in providing security and predictability to the multilateral trading system. The Members recognise that it seems to preserve the rights and obligations of Members under the covered agreement and to clarify the existing provisions of those agreements in accordance with the customary rules of interpretation of the Public International Law.” According to the Panel of the US Section 301, Trade Act, the DSU is one of the most important instruments of the WTO in protecting the security and predictability of the Multilateral Trading System.’

Settlement of Dispute through Multilateral Procedures.’

¹¹ Peter Vondin Bossche, *The Law and Policies of World Trade Organisation*

¹² US-Shrimp Complaint by India, Malaysia, Pakistan and Thailand

¹³ sbestors complaint by Canada

¹⁴ Approval and Marketing of Biotech Products, Complained by the US; Canada and Argentina

The object and purpose of the dispute settlement system is for Members to settle dispute with other Members through the multilateral procedures of the DSU rather through unilateral action¹⁵.

Article 23.1 of the DSU states: ‘When Members seek redressal of a violation of obligations or other nullification or impairment of benefits under the covered agreements or an impediment to the attainment of any objective of the covered agreements, they shall have recourse to and abide by, the rules and procedures of this understanding.’”

Thus, the Article 23.1 of the DSU imposes a general obligation to redress a violation of WTO law through the multilateral DSU procedures and not through unilateral action.’

Article 23.2 of the DSU, WTO Members may not make a unilateral determination that a violation of WTO law has occurred and may not take retaliation measures unilaterally in the case of violation of WTO Law.

Settlement of dispute through consultation, if possible’

‘According to *Article 3.7 of the DSU*, the aim of dispute settlement mechanism is to secure a possible solution, a solution mutually acceptable to the parties to a dispute and consistent with the covered agreement is very much to be preferred.’

It implies that DSU is inclined to resolve disputes through mutually acceptable terms between the parties through negotiation rather than adjudication thus, consultation is the initial step in any dispute resolution proceedings¹⁶. To resolve dispute through consultation is not only affordable but also more beneficial for long-term trade relations with the other party to the dispute than adjudication by a panel.

Settlement of dispute and clarification of WTO Law’

As per *Article 3.2 of the DSU*, the role and purpose of the dispute resolution mechanism is not limited to protect the rights and obligations of Members under covered agreements, but also to provide clarification of the existing provisions of those agreements. The covered agreements might have provisions that suffer with gaps and the main fambiguity; thus elucidation and simplification of those

¹⁵ See Article 23 of the DSU

¹⁶ The Appellate Body Report US-Certain EC products, para 116-21. The Appellate Body in this case uphold the panels finding of violation of Article 3.7 of the DSU.

provisions is necessary. However, Article 3.2 states, “The recommendations and rulings of the DSU cannot add to or diminish the rights and obligations provided in the covered agreement.”

Settlement of Dispute in Good faith’

Article 3.10 of the DSU outlines the use of conflict resolution processes, stating that all Members must participate in them in an effort to settle the problem. In other words, it is part of the goal and purpose of the WTO dispute settlement system that parties interested in the process engage with a sincere desire to see the dispute resolved.’

PART IV: ORGANS OF WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT

The main objective for the establishment of the WTO is to implement a proper adjudication system of dispute settlement. Trade relations might often lead to conflicting interests and it becomes necessary to set up a healthy mode to settle these conflicts through some neutral procedure based on some sound and agreed legal base; to ensure peace. Thus, is the purpose of establishing the Dispute Resolution Mechanism envisaged in the WTO agreements. The WTO dispute settlement machinery functions almost like a “Court of International Trade” that has compulsory and specific jurisdiction. The conflicts are settled largely with the help of rules of law and the final decisions are binding on the parties. Sanctions may be imposed if decisions are not complied with. This part examines the roles of ‘*Dispute Settlement Body* the Panel and the *Appellate Body*.’

The machinery involved in the system of dispute settlement in the WTO are,

- (i) ‘Dispute Settlement Body (political institutions)’
- (ii) ‘Dispute Settlement Panels (independent judicial type institutions).’
- (iii) ‘Standing Appellate Body.’
- (iv) ‘Other Bodies and Persons involved in WTO Dispute settlement.’

The WTO entrusts the adjudication of disputes at the first instance to panels and at the appellate level to the standing Appellate Body.

4.1 'DISPUTE SETTLEMENT BODY'

The WTO Dispute Settlement System is administered by the Dispute Settlement Body (DSB)¹⁷. Through the DSB, the General Council fulfils its obligations under the DSU. Article IV.3 of the WTO Agreement states that the General Council shall meet as deemed necessary to carry out the duties and obligations assigned to the '*Dispute Settlement Body* under the Dispute Resolution Agreement.' The 'Dispute Settlement Body' has the power to elect its own Chairman and shall establish any procedural norms it considers appropriate to ensure smooth functioning out its duties. Consequently, the DSB has the '*power to create and accept panels and Reports of Appellate Body, monitor the applications for decisions and recommendations, and approve the suspension of obligations under the covered agreements*'¹⁸.

4.2 'DISPUTE SETTLEMENT PANELS OF WTO PANELS'

Are quasi-judicial institutions. In a way, they serve as tribunals tasked with first-instance resolution of Member issues. They typically consist of three experts, although in extreme circumstances, five experts may be chosen at random. This indicates that the WTO does not have a permanent panel. Any impartial, highly competent individual is eligible to participate as a panellist. The WTO Secretariat may draw panellists from the list of potential government and business partners or nongovernmental persons¹⁹. A person appointed as panellist serves in an individual capacity as an independent identity and not as a government representative or as a representative of any organisation²⁰. At WTO; the initial step of resolution of disputes is carried out by an ad hoc 'Dispute Settlement Panel.' In order to initialize the adjudication, process several stages have to be passed through, such as,

- A. 'Panel request.'
- B. 'Establishment of a Panel'
- C. 'Composition of panel'
- D. 'Terms of reference of the panel'
- E. 'Standard of review applied by panels.'
- F. 'The exercise of judicial economy by panel.'
- G. 'Characteristics of panel report; and

¹⁷ Article 2.1 of the DSU

¹⁸ Article 2.1 of the DSU

¹⁹ Article 8.4 of the DSU.

²⁰ Article 8.4 of the DSU.

H. 'The role of the WTO secretariat'

4.3 'THE APPELLATE BODY'

As per the *Article 17.1 of the DSU*, 'there shall be a *standing Appellate Body* to be established by the DSB. Unlike Panels, Appellate Body is a permanent international tribunal consisting of body of seven members entrusted with the task of reviewing the legal aspects of the Panel Reports. Thus, the Appellate Body is the second and final stage in the judiciary part of the Dispute Settlement System. This system was not in existence in the old GATT 1947. This Appellate Body is an innovation of the Uruguay Round of Multilateral Trade Negotiations, so that in the current dispute settlement system, individual Member of the WTO is no longer able to prevent the adoption of the Panel Report, unless they have at least the tacit approval of all other Members represented in the DSB. The automatic nature of the adoption of the Panel Report not only denies the 'losing party' the chance of blocking the Report but also takes away the possibility for parties or other Members to reject panel reports due to substantive disagreement with the Panel's legal analysis.'

As per *Article 17.13 of the DSU*, 'if a party files an appeal against a Panel Report, the Appellate Body reviews the challenged legal issues and may uphold, reverse or modify the panel's findings²¹.'

This includes the following:

- 'The membership of Appellate Body'
- 'The institutional structure of the Appellate Body'
- 'Access to Appellate review'
- 'Scope of Appellate review' and
- 'Mandate of Appellate Body'

4.4 OTHER BODIES AND PERSONS INVOLVED IN WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT'

Other bodies and individuals engaged in the settlement include a number of others besides the DSB, Panels, and Appellate Body; that works as an alternative to panel and appellate body adjudication. According to DSU Article 25.1, parties to a dispute may choose arbitration. According to Article 25.2 of

²¹ Article 17.13 of the DSU

the DSU, the arbitration and the processes to be followed must be agreed upon by the parties. Therefore, the parties to the dispute are free to forego following the DSU's conventional processes and to settle on their own set of rules and guidelines for the arbitration, including how to choose an arbitrator. The points in contention must also be expressly defined by the parties. The parties must give their consent to the arbitration proceedings before they begin agreement among all WTO Members to use arbitration. Only with the consent of the parties involved in the arbitration may other Members join the dispute. The arbitration award must be abided by the parties involved, and once it is made, it must be reported to the DSB and the appropriate councils and committees in charge of the agreement(s) in question²². The arbitration award declared under Article 25 is subject to the provisions of Articles 21 and 22 of the DSU.'

PART V: WTO AND GLOBAL JUSTICE

In terms of global justice issues the WTO contributes in a complex way that reveals both its strengths and weaknesses. Through its core ideas of non-discrimination and the dispute system the WTO is attempting to set up a balanced framework for international commerce. These aspects foster equal legal rights for all member states irrespective of their financial condition.

The real performance of the WTO is seen by many to advantage well-developed countries more than nascent ones and ultimately perpetuates international inequity. An important problem is the disparity in influence during trade discussions. Wealthy countries enjoy greater financial strength and professional abilities to negotiate agreements and favor trade policies that fit their objectives. When it comes to intellectual property rights and agricultural subsidies advanced economies frequently gain an edge over less developed country.

In the WTO's dispute settling process developing nations typically face challenges since they usually lack the financial and legal expertise required to conduct extended legal proceedings against more powerful nations. The emphasis placed by WTO rules on market liberalization has the potential to exploit weaker domestic industries in developing countries by more powerful international competitors damaging local economies and livelihoods.

Recently, the Appellate body is non-functional; the panel of 7 members is vacant and there have been little to no efforts to ensure that it is in operation. This hampers the adjudication process and parties who

²² Article 25.2 and 25.3 of the DSU.

have won the initial round of adjudication are left helpless as soon as appeal is filed. It will remain pending till anew panel is constituted; thus, hampering global justice.

To strengthen global justice at the WTO level , reforms in the working of the dispute resolution mechanism is necessary. It is important to enhance the roles of developing countries in decisions and to offer them increased support for capacity development to tackle trade barriers that reproduce disparities. Goals for trade reforms ought to emphasize fairness that enables countries to reap significant rewards from overseas trading schemes.

It can be said, that the WTO has contributed to a more orderly global trade system, its impact on global justice remains contentious. To achieve global justice in its genuine form; it is necessary to address the power imbalances that currently limit the equitable distribution of trade benefits.

PART VI: SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The provisions in the WTO Agreement and DSU should be scrupulously implemented. For example, Anti-Dumping and countervailing duties ensures transparency in all transactions so that other governments should also know that the situation and decisions are not taken in an arbitrary fashion. Dispute Settlement Rules are to be modified so as to have no loopholes in the existing system. Conciliation and mediations are to be encouraged so as to avoid loss of time, energy and money. To add certainty, predictability and fairness to the international trading system, the DSU should be reorganized so that undue interference of politics can be held at bay. The WTO dispute settlement mechanism has been widely accepted as one of the important innovations in the international economic development of the 20th century. But, there are certain short-comings creeping in the system at its application level. So, that has to be removed. The researcher would like to make some suggestions to make the system more effective. The present system which is closer to the legal adjudication method should be made without delay, as it is universally accepted that “delayed justice is denied justice”. If a decision in international trade dispute is delayed, the loser would have to suffer high pecuniary losses, that sometimes may result in the very loss of the business. This has to be considered while framing laws on trade disputes.

This study generates more questions for future research than the answers it provides. One question comes up all the time. ‘Has the WTO become a sort of ‘World Trade Court?’ One of the major areas of any future research would be to disassociate the case lodged by Member countries against a particular Member (Preferably the United States and the European Communities from the samples chosen by the

researcher) and examine the results from that perspective. A comparative study of WTO and ICJ is another possible area for future research. The adoption of panels and Appellate body recommendations by the Dispute Settlement Body, as if, it were a super judicial authority is another suitable area for future research. The forum at which the developing countries challenge the WTO incompatibilities of their developed counterpoints is another major area for future research. Though it is difficult, there is a possibility to analyse the ongoing scenario and come to a near definite conclusion on the relationship between the annual publication of Trade Policy Review (TPRS) reports and the DSB in the current frame work. However, on the basis of the cases analysed in the previous PARTs, we see that the Appellate Body report published annually needs many more publications to enhance the spread of the Appellate Body reports. The annual publication of the WTO's Trade Policy Review report could well be considered as an extensively prepared background note for the developing countries. This helps the developing countries much more than the developed countries. A systematic reform at the WTO, with particular stress on the DSB, would resolve most of the serious challenges against the WTO and its Dispute Settlement Body.

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